

TRADITIONAL AND MODERN HUMAN RESOURCE PRACTICES ON INDIAN CORPORATE SECTOR

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ABSTRACT

The 90's was a period of Liberation, Privatization and Globalization (LPG show) in India, which went for making Indian economy one of the quickest developing economies on the planet. With consistent changes, arrangement changes and high FDI venture, 21st century India has turned into an able place for business speculation that can possibly make a positive effect on the worldwide economy too.

Contracting business outskirts and globalization have brought about business, social and ability trade among nations, which has caused serious modifications in HR capacities around the world. From taking care of large scale issues including worldwide workforce and virtual group the board to smaller scale issues, for example, worker directing and individual supporting, the job of a HR proficient has turned out to be ultra-various nowadays.

Key-Words: LPG, FDI, SHRM, Six Sigma Practices.

INTRODUCTION

Post globalization and technological advancement, the world of HRM is changing rapidly. Constant environment changes have led to several issues in HR domain of India in regards to recruitment, engagement, HR technology, employee training, workforce management etc. Today, Indian HR community works in a compact, globalized ecosystem which needs a technology-driven, trust-worthy, faster and automated HR system. An automated system that allows HR to manage, analyze and govern centrally is what HR leaders seek today. A technologically-advanced HR system that can provide access to relevant candidate data, analytics and revenue information is likely to become the key to resolving such HR issues; a tool that HR need the most.

Traditional Recruiting Methods:

1. Newspapers:

Newspapers are among the oldest methods of communicating about vacancies to people. They are read by a major segment of people even today.

2. Local Employment Office: Postings vacancies at local employment offices is an effective way and they usually operate a wide networked database, training programmes for candidates, financial support hiring programmes for further assistance.

3. Hiring Internally:

It is a time tested method and one of the easiest methods to hire right person for the job. The team knows the existing employees and their potential, working styles, background, and performance. Hence internal hiring works well.

4. Temporary Employment Agencies:

Temporary Employment Agencies are one of the most used methods for short listing candidates and finding people who suit the organization's preference and experience requirements.

Modern Recruiting Methods:

1. Tapping Smart Phones: Smart Phones have made it simple to interface with the world and the youthful age is stuck to it. Any page can be gotten to through it. Coordinators utilize this and collaborate with the hopefuls by giving information about their organizations web based, optimizing company's portal utilizing sms for correspondences

2. Tap in Social Media:

Facebook and Twitter are utilized more than some other medium these days. Individuals use it for everything running from news to refreshing their activity necessities. Associations and enrollment specialists utilize this medium to draw in with their planned applicants, workers, and even with exchange supporters, in a couple of cases.

3. Event Recruitment:

Companies sponsor events which are identified with their ethic esteem, esteem which they wish to speak to through their affiliation. It causes them gain notoriety and their message goes over a wide net of individuals. Basic disapproved of individuals accumulate at such places and such occasions are an incredible method to enlist appropriate representatives.

Table 1: Managing the HR function strategically

Stage	Characterstics
Basics	Focusing on paying , hiring and firing people
Functional Growth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Have programs for recruitment , compensation, and benefits, affirmative action, labor relations, training and development etc • Lack line in management involvement
Controlled Growth	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HR program and activities being evaluated • HR programs are focused on the organizations need • Line managers are aware of HR program • Programs are often specialized and decentralized
Functional Integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HR program are integrated • Programs are related to problems areas rather that specialized functions • Involved in organizational development , productivity , improvement
Cross Functional Integration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • HR programs are fully integrated into plans and activities of other corporate areas such as marketing, finance, production • Line managers become the driving force behind HR program

(Source:- Baird & Meshoulam, The HRS Matrix: Managing the HR function strategically, 1984)

Challenges

The 4 challenges that an Indian Human Resource industry experiences in the 21st century while running their departments.

1. Recruitment

To balance the obtainable workforce or reinstate the lost staff, Recruitment of top-talent is a key challenge faced by the human resource department. Finding staff with the right mix of skills and self-driven qualities is a major task in itself. Recruitment is carried out by the internal HR department or with third-party coordination, but the efficient central management of the same also is important.

How to Hire Better employee?

A selection representative need to record, parse and assess each moment detail of a competitor. In any case, with the assistance of HR pre-contract enlistment stages, pulling in best ability and employing them gets a lot simpler. Constant handling of CVs, quicker competitor commitment, simple arranging are few advantages of utilizing enrollment programming.

An additional advantage of utilizing such enlistment apparatuses is eliminated future enrollment cost and time as the instrument gives you're a vault of dynamic/latent competitors. Speeding the whole enlistment process and computerizing the equivalent is the answer for contract savvy and better.

2. Retention

Employees are the life saver of an organization and organizations contribute huge time, in addition to cash to guarantee greatest profitability and enthusiasm of their laborers. Another imperative obligation of HR is to ensure their prior significant resource – the employees.

How to Retain Employees?

Employee retention is a fine balance between company culture, employee engagement, remuneration, recognition and incentives. HR department needs to provide a balanced combination of all five to satisfy employees without compromising the company's interests. Timely upgrading of employee retention policies is a must while facing fierce market competition.

3. Productivity:

Another significant assignment that a human asset group performs is support of 'Ideal Productivity' among specialists. At the point when profitability is low, HR has to know the torment zones including poor working practices or absence of assets. Powerful correspondence of agony zones to higher administration and giving a constant answer for representatives is likewise critical.

How to Enhance Productivity?

While most HRs recognize that their activity involves setting up approaches, methods, individuals the executives programs, and so on.; not very many endeavors to associate components to expand worker yield, commitment, maintenance and others. While actualizing the correct device for efficiency improvement, it is vital for HRs to fuse three beneath recorded components inside the association.

1. Technology to enhance activities.
2. Reviewing existing set-up.
3. Implementing a consistent enhancement approach.

The vital partnership of previously mentioned components empowers consistent development of an association without essentially growing its size, consumption or foundation.

4. Talent Management

Another principle capacity of HR group is to oversee, administer and anchoring top gifts. Ability the executives starts from on boarding right competitor pursued by representative commitment and worker maintenance. A deliberately shaped ability the executives method enables spotters to hold extraordinary workers.

Research materials and methods:

Field Survey-

Research Instruments: The research instruments used for collecting primary data were:

- Questionnaire and
- Interviews (a patterned interview approach)

The questionnaire (REFERENCE SECTION) comprises of questions pertaining to:-

- Ranking of the possible drivers for introducing e-technology to the HR systems.
- Ranking of the barriers to progress in the e-HRM journey.
- Usage of e-technology for the HR functions. For this purpose

18 HR functions were specified. These are- Recruitment and Selection, Payroll Management, Leave Management, Attendance Management, Manpower Planning, Communication, Training and Development, Performance Management, Induction, Selecting Benefits, Compensation Planning, Competency Mapping, Career Planning, Succession Planning, Employee Transition, Travel Management, Exit Management and Maintaining Employee Records.

- Usage of HR Service delivery tools like ESS, MSS, Web 2.0, Intranet and e-Learning Portal.
- Nature of Sourcing solutions adopted by companies for enabling e-technology to HR systems- In-house/Outsourced/ Software-as-a-service.
- Perception of respondents on a five-point scale regarding their company's position in the e-HRM journey today vs after 5 years. The scale ranges from 'Neither understand nor value e-HRM' to 'complete incorporation of e-HRM strategy into the business model'.
- Expectation of respondents w.r.t.-
- The e-HRM system being successful in satisfying employees in their HR needs

- The benefits from e-HRM justifying the expenditure incurred on the same.
- Opinion of respondents on various aspects of the e-HRM functioning- Resource Management, Compensation and Rewards, Performance Management, Training and Development, Employee Relations and some general aspects like user-friendliness, timeliness, etc. A five-point scale with the following degrees was used-
- Strongly disagree/ Disagree/ Undecided/ Agree/ Strongly agree.
- Open ended questions were also included in the questionnaire to assess the pre-requisites and challenges of e-HRM and to elicit suggestions from respondents.

Sampling Design:

The analysis of data is based on the following classification:

Services Sector including- Accounting/Consulting/Taxation; Airlines & Aviation; Banks; Export Houses; Financial Services; High- tech Services; Hospitals/Healthcare; Hotels/Resorts; Insurance; Law/Legal Consultants; Management/Engineering /Environment Consultants; Media/Entertainment; Mutual Fund/Stock Broking; Office Automation; Placement /HR Training Consultants; Retail; Security; Travel & Tourism.

Manufacturing Sector including- Auto Ancillaries/ Auto components; Automobiles; Capital Goods/Machine Manufacturing; Cement; Chemicals; Consumer Goods - Durables/Home Appliances; Electrical & Electronics; Engineering; FMCG; Food Processing/Beverages;Garment/Textiles/Accessories; Gems/Jewelleries/Watches; Iron and Steel; Leather Shoes/Accessories ;Metals/Mining; Paints; Petrochemicals/Oil/ Gas/Refineries; Pharmaceuticals/Bio-tech; Power/Energy; Rubber/Plastic/Glass/Wood; Sports & Toys.

A classification of companies into MNCs and Non-MNCs has also been taken for analysis.

Statement of Hypotheses:

H01: There is no significant difference between groups and within group's w.r.t. the considered driver for introducing e-HRM systems in companies.

H02: There is no significant difference in usage of e-technology for the considered HR function between Services vs Manufacturing groups.

H03: There is no significant difference in the usage of e-technology for the considered HR function between MNC vs Non-MNC groups.

H04: There is no significant difference in the usage of the considered HR Service Delivery

Tool between Services vs manufacturing groups.

H05: There is no significant difference in the usage of the considered HR Service Delivery Tool between MNC vs Non-MNC groups.

H06: There is no significant difference between Services vs manufacturing groups regarding their perception of their company's position in the e-HRM journey today.

H07: There is no significant difference between MNC vs Non-MNC groups regarding their perception of their company's position in the e-HRM journey today.

H08: There is no significant difference between groups and within groups w.r.t. perception of respondents regarding their company's position in the e-HRM journey today.

H09: There is no significant difference between Services vs Manufacturing groups regarding their perception of their company's position in the e-HRM journey after five years.

H010: There is no significant difference between MNC vs Non-MNC groups regarding their perception of their company's position in the e-HRM journey after five years.

H011: There is no significant difference between groups and within groups w.r.t. perception of respondents regarding their company's position in the e-HRM journey after five years.

H012: There is no significant difference in the perception of the Services group regarding their company's position in the e-HRM journey today vs 'after 5 years'.

H013: There is no significant difference in the perception of the Manufacturing group regarding their company's position in the e-HRM journey today vs 'after 5 years'.

H014: There is no significant difference in the perception of the 'MNC' group regarding their company's position in the e-HRM journey today vs 'after 5 years'.

H015: There is no significant difference in the perception of the 'Non- MNC' group regarding their company's position in the e-HRM journey today vs 'after 5 years'.

H016: There is no significant difference between groups and within groups w.r.t the considered barrier to progress in the e-HRM journey.

H017: There is no significant difference in the expectation of respondents w.r.t. e-HRM being successful in satisfying employees in their HR needs between Services vs Manufacturing groups.

H018: There is no significant difference in the expectation of respondents w.r.t. e-HRM being

successful in satisfying employees in their HR needs between MNC vs Non-MNC groups.

H019: There is no significant difference in the expectation of respondents w.r.t. the benefits from e-HRM justifying the expenditure on the same between Services vs Manufacturing groups.

H020: There is no significant difference in the expectation of respondents w.r.t. the benefits from e-HRM justifying the expenditure on the same between MNC vs Non-MNC groups.

H021: There is no significant difference in overall opinion on the considered aspects of e-HRM between Services vs manufacturing groups.

H022: There is no significant difference in overall opinion on the considered aspects of e-HRM between MNC vs Non-MNC groups.

Table 3.1 % of Respondents by Type of Sector (Services/Manufacturing)

	Frequency	Percent
Services	344	34.40
Manufacturing	656	65.60
TOTAL	1000	100.00

Table 3.2 % of Respondents by Type of Company (MNC/Non-MNC)

	Frequency	Percent
MNC	170	17.00
Non-MNC	830	83.00
TOTAL	1000	100.00

Table 3.3 % of Respondents (MNC/Non- MNC)*(Services/Manufacturing)

Type of Company		Type of Sector		Total
		Services	Manufacturing	
MNC	Count	110	60	170
	% within Type of Sector	31.98%	9.15%	17.00%
Non-MNC	Count	234	596	830
	% within Type of Sector	68.02%	90.85%	83.00%
Total	Count	344	656	1000
	% within Type of Sector	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%

Table 3.4 : % of Respondents by Size of Company (Annual Turn-over)

Annual Turnover (Rs. Cr.)	Frequency	Percent
<= 10 Crores	92	9.20
10-100 Crores	367	36.70
100-250 Crores	187	18.70
250-500 Crores	105	10.50
500- 1000 Crores	109	10.90
1000-2500 Crores	77	7.70
2500-5000 Crores	34	3.40
> 5000 Crores	29	2.90
Total	1000	100.00

Table 3.5: % of Respondents by Size of Company (No. of Employees)

No. of Employees	Frequency	Percent
101-250	172	17.20
251-500	166	16.60
501-1000	340	34.00
1001-2500	172	17.20
2501-5000	68	6.80
> 5000	82	8.20
Total	1000	100.00

Table 3.6: Size of Company (Annual Turn-over) * Type of Sector (Services/Manufacturing)

Annual Turn-over (Rs. Cr.)		Type of Sector		Total
		Services	Manufacturing	
<= 10 Crores	Count	81	11	92
	% within Type of Sector	23.50%	1.70%	9.20%
10-100 Crores	Count	170	197	367
	% within Type of Sector	49.40%	30.10%	36.70%
100-250 Crores	Count	39	148	187
	% within Type of Sector	11.30%	22.60%	18.70%
250-500 Crores	Count	14	91	105
	% within Type of Sector	4.10%	13.90%	10.50%
500- 1000 Crores	Count	20	89	109
	% within Type of Sector	5.80%	13.60%	10.90%
1000-2500 Crores	Count	12	65	77
	% within Type of Sector	3.50%	9.90%	7.70%
2500-5000 Crores	Count	5	29	34
	% within Type of Sector	1.50%	4.40%	3.40%
> 5000 Crores	Count	3	26	29
	% within Type of Sector	0.90%	4.00%	2.90%
Total	Count	344	656	1000
	% within Type of Sector	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%

Table 3.7 Size of Company (No. of Employees) * Type of Sector (Services/Manufacturing)

No. of Employees		Type of Sector		Total
		Services	Manufacturing	
101-250	Count	151	21	172
	% within Type of Sector	43.90%	3.20%	17.20%
251-500	Count	70	96	166
	% within Type of Sector	20.30%	14.70%	16.60%
501-1000	Count	60	280	340
	% within Type of Sector	17.40%	42.70%	34.00%
1001-2500	Count	32	140	172
	% within Type of Sector	9.30%	21.40%	17.20%
2501-5000	Count	19	49	68
	% within Type of Sector	5.50%	7.50%	6.80%
> 5000	Count	12	70	82
	% within Type of Sector	3.50%	10.50%	8.20%
Total	Count	344	656	1000
	% within Type of Sector	100.00%	100.00%	100.00%

Strategies to Follow:

Talent management flows from the organization's mission, vision, values and goals. When stated clearly and effectively, this enables every employee to vision their role and valuation within the organization.

1. Hire best fit for your company and available position.
2. Communicate 'Terms of Service ' clearly.
3. Provide effective on boarding training and development opportunities.
4. Provide on-going coaching, mentoring and feedback to engage your employees.
5. Effective implementation of performance review and recognition system is vital.

8 Real-Time Challenges HR will be dealing by 2020: Be that as it may, today the situation has experienced a few changes and India is all the more deliberately situated in the worldwide corporate guide and HR the board (HRM) has turned out to be very mind boggling, particularly after computerized disturbance attacked the area. Enterprises are confronting umpteen number of HR challenges that should be tended to. Worldwide sentiments see India's human asset as a minimal effort, exceptionally gifted, committed and learned workforce subsequently it has likewise turned into a noteworthy redistributing ground. Then again, it's a given that, the general area of HR isn't without its issues and preliminaries. The HR in India, particularly in the 21st century, faces certain difficulties, in spite of its three noteworthy jobs of—value-based, transformational, and transitional. With a consistently changing corporate India, HR challenges are good to go to build complex and obviously that HR chiefs must know about this reality.

1. Managing globalization

It is imperative that HR work force learn appropriate individuals the executives rehearses before wanting to actualize them, particularly the ones that are worldwide in nature. Nowadays it has turned out to be very trying for the HR to teach its workforce on how globalization can be utilized and how a solitary worker benefits or is influenced by it. Rather than forcing new practices upon them, it is ideal to study the prevailing practices which are in place.

2. Retaining talent, especially millennials

Holding is likely a standout amongst the most huge HR challenges that the space should manage in 2017. What's more, holding recent college grads is the most Herculean assignment for present day HR. Ability poaching and relentless rivalry has given a catalyst of high compensation to the meriting applicant. Occupation searchers have picked up part of introduction and have turned out to be exceedingly eager too. Which is the reason they are dependably on a post for better chances? This sort of a pattern is watched for the most part in the IT/ITeS segment. HR work force in this area really discover it a test to hold its representatives.

3. Developing leadership skills Creating future pioneers is basically a troublesome errand. It isn't just about growing right delicate aptitudes so as to shape future pioneers. Since the worldwide financial situation is extremely unstable, and dynamic, what is required presently is a range of abilities in the workforce that recognizes them as future pioneers. Creating future pioneers is a noteworthy HR challenge that should be tended to later on.

4. Managing organisational change Change the executives is one more test that the HR keeps on looking in the 21st century. With enormous associations coordinating Six Sigma rehearses in their organizations, managing change the executives is ending up even troublesome with each passing day. The mechanical development situation is to such an extent that, there is a colossal interest for 'change' that must be realized inside every one of the parts of the general public. Be that as it may, there's obstruction from different sides. It is a tremendous test for the HR to check those opposing powers lastly execute new hierarchical changes.

5. Developing work ethics: With the worldwide economy experiencing high points and low points, India likewise needs to hold up under the brunt of the equivalent to some degree—if not all things considered. Representative ethics and faithfulness are being tried consistently. In such attempting occasions, it is ending up somewhat troublesome for the HR the board to guarantee legitimate improvement of hard working attitudes. Re-imparting esteems like sympathy, hard working attitudes, regard for the feeble and elderly are turning into a matter of worry for all—even HR faculty inside associations.

6. Developing and nurturing accountability

Since the development of Six Sigma approaches, the resilience levels in associations for blunders and real slip-ups have gone down impressively. It is a test which HR the board in India is confronting like its worldwide partners. It is difficult to prepare individuals to bear duty.

7. Managing workforce stress and employment relations

HR the executives is the essence of an association. They procure individuals as well as guarantee that they sustain representatives, so last stays with an association for a more drawn out timeframe. In the event that the HR the board isn't sympathetic towards its workforce, it doesn't help in representative relations. This reality is quick turning into a test for all HR people group in India in the present occasions.

8. Managing workforce diversity

With globalization and India's economy seeing a quickened development, associations are presently compelled to rely upon employing individuals from a wide range of foundations, ethnicities and even nations. Obviously this has prompted a totally new measurement to working environment assorted variety. Dealing with an assorted workforce is genuinely a requesting errand for HRM in India in the present occasions.

The year passed by observed more weight and worry in the work environment: a shaky economy, all the more difficult work hours, and employment cuts. Also, it is simply expected to increment. The world over, human asset (HR) groups are attempting to keep pace. "The best way to have an upper hand will be to continue rethinking the essentials of HR," says Bhuvaneshwar Naik, worldwide head of ability the executives at SAP, a German programming partnership.

Challenge in talent acquisition

The effect of robotization, however effectively noticeable in the previous couple of years, may move toward becoming reason for stress, particularly in a nation like India, with its administrations enterprises. As more occupations get computerized, ability obtaining will enter another stage—individuals will require explicit aptitudes to get work. Furthermore, when that

ability is a piece of the workforce, holding it will likewise require consistent exertion from the HR group.

Russell Rozario, vice-president, HR, Metropolis Health Services, points out another challenge: HR teams may have to look at related industries to hire talent. “For example, we are reaching out to the retail space because people have some knowledge about the healthcare space, or to telecom, because they have worked within an industrial distribution network.”

Staying relevant

Organizations have traditionally trained their employees, but now, the responsibility will shift to employees, believes Rituparna Chakraborty, co-founder of staffing firm TeamLease. “While skilled people will be good at certain roles, companies will have to look at people who are curious to learn. These are the ones who can seamlessly move from one role to the other,” she explains. Chakraborty suggests a mix of apprenticeships as well as massive open online courses or certifications to stay relevant in the rapidly changing professional scenario.

In an article published last year for the World Economic Forum, Stephane Kasriel, chief executive officer, Upwork, a global freelancing platform, said that “no matter how much training is on offer, companies probably won’t have all the tools they need and freelancers will begin filling those gaps”. Kasriel believes that to be relevant, employees will need to keep renewing their skills as often as every five years.

Digital will be key

As more millennials join the organized workforce, HR will have to employ analytics to understand the needs of people in a more customized, individual-specific manner, and provide solutions through the use of mobile technology and newer platforms. The possibilities are endless: mobile-friendly platforms for communication, performance management, continuous feedback and pulse surveys, easier HR systems, automated processes, chatbots, and more.

“Automation of HR processes must take place to reduce effort spent in redundant processes. The time made available through automation can be used to truly partner with business and people, towards better employee experience,” says Richard Lobo, head of HR at Infosys.

Redefining diversity

Diversity won't just be demographic, says T.K. Srirang, senior general manager and head of HR, ICICI Bank. “The approach to diversity is likely to become more nuanced where organizations need to look at harnessing thought diversity as an important aspect of workforce diversity. The focus is on harnessing the full potential of people by acknowledging and encouraging each person's unique perspective and ways of thinking.”

With the practice of people spending almost their entire working lives in one company coming to an end, the freelance industry will get a boost. A diverse workforce will now mean a mix of full-time and freelance employees, young and old, and all genders.

“Diverse workforce is a trend we can see, but it will make employee engagement more complex,” says Bernard Martyris, chief of HR for the outsourcing firm VFS Global.

Performance management

In all likelihood, ideas like performance ratings, year-end rankings and reviews will be phased out.

“Continuous dialogue between the employee and his manager, his clients, and even HR will become more important. It will touch every aspect of the employee's life cycle in a company, starting from how he is welcomed, how his work hours are, the reviews coming from his manager or his peers,” explains Naik.

Changes in work 'space'

According to a study by US-based furniture manufacturer Steelcase, lack of privacy is the foremost complaint among employees. Not many offices have been able to juggle collaboration with privacy. This year, organizations will have to reconcile people's needs for both types of

settings. “Instead of providing only open-plan work settings, organizations should create settings in which people have a mix of both open and structured spaces,” says Praveen Rawal, managing director, Steelcase India.

It is not just workplace layout that will undergo change, but the space itself. “Work (out) places, working from home, pop-up workplaces will come into prominence, backed by improving infrastructure around IT bandwidth and cloud-based solutions,” explains Chakraborty.

Focus on data analytics

As companies become more reliant on technology, every step of the employee life-cycle will be recorded. The extent of data available with the HR team will go beyond the date of joining and remuneration increase. Take a seven-step sales process, for instance. If an employee is good in the first five, but data shows he is taking too long in the negotiation and agreement closure stages, companies could offer training for the last two steps.

Not just training, data analytics will also enable HR to correlate reasons for attrition and client loss, for instance, and take redressal measures.

According to Ashutosh Telang, chief human resources officer, Marico Ltd, a consumer goods company, “We will see an onslaught of even more digitization, artificial intelligence, augmented reality and robotics at the workplace in the coming year. Data analytics will facilitate sharper people insights and predictive analytics for proactive and better-quality HR decisions.”

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